

INTERFEROMETRIC SENTINEL-1 DEM GENERATION: A CASE STUDY IN TEHRAN, IRAN

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ABSTRACT:

Today with respect to improvements of technology and importance of generating DEM from every region in our country, the importance of satellite remote sensing is more sensible. One of the main topics in satellite remote sensing is radar remote sensing. In recent years a number of satellites have been launched to capture SAR information from Earth surface. The last project is Sentinel, that Sentinel-1 generates SAR data. It generates images with medium spatial resolution from the Earth every 12 days. In this paper, precision and potential of DEM from these images have been analysed. Images are taken from Tehran and the suburbs. In the experiments both mountain and flat areas have been used. SAR interferometry with two pass repeat is used to generate DEM. Generated DEM using Sentinel-1 and SAR interferometry method is compared with reference DEM with one-meter precision. The results show that in flat area, height precision (standard deviation) of DEM is 1.26 meter and in mountain area is 10.32 meter.

1. INTRODUCTION

A Digital Elevation Model or DEM is physical representation of terrain and topography that is modelled by a digital 3D model. DEMs have various applications in many fields. DEM achieves from different methods such as remote sensing. Nowadays, DEM is generated by optical stereo image pairs, Synthetic Aperture (SAR) images (such as radargrammetry) (Eftekhary, 2013), Lidar Data and etc. One important of the methods for generate DEM is SAR interferometry (Makineci, 2016), (Lazecky, 2017). Space-borne Interferometric SAR is an advanced geodetic tool, featured by its all-day and all-weather working abilities, wide spatial coverage, fine spatial resolution, high measurement precision and no need for ground instrumentation. By extracting the phase differences between two SAR images got over the same area but different times, SAR Interferometry (InSAR) can be used to create DEM or measure the ground displacement occurred during the time interval (Hu, 2014). Several mission are started at space-borne radar imaging in recent year. One of them is sentinel-1 (Ghannadi, 2015). Sentinel-1 has an unbeatable mapping ability. In interferometric wide swath (IW) mode, three subswaths imaged in the novel Terrain Observation by Progressive Scans (TOPS) SAR mode result in a total swath width of 250 km. Sentinel-1 is suitable for mapping and interferometric monitoring at medium resolution. The interferometric processing of TOPS data however requires special consideration of the signal properties, resulting from the ScanSAR-type burst imaging and the antenna beam steering in azimuth. The high Doppler rate in azimuth sets very stringent co-registration requirements, making the use of enhanced spectral diversity (ESD) necessary to obtain the required fine azimuth co-registration accuracy (Yagüe, 2016).

In the next section, case study and data for generating DEM and evaluating precision are introduced.

2. STUDY AREA AND DATA

In this paper, sentinel-1 images are used for generate DEM. These images are taken from Tehran and the suburbs

2.1 Study Area

The region of study in this research to do experiments and generate DEM, is in Tehran, Iran. Tehran is located in north of Iran and south of Alborz mountains and is 112 kilometres far from the south of Caspian Sea. The elevation of this city is from 1050 meters in south up to 2000 meters in north of it

2.2 Data and Images

In this research Sentinel-1 stereo images are used to generate DEM that Tehran is located in these images. These images are shown in figure 1.

Some information and characteristics about these stereo images are shown in Table (1).

Imaging Date (Master)	Imaging Date (Slave)	Orbit Direction	Incidence Angle
2015/03/13	2015/05/24	ascending	33.8 Degree
Spatial Resolution	Polarization	Channel	Type and Processing Level
5×20	VV	C	IW-SLC

Table 1. specifications of sentinel-1 images from Tehran, Iran

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Sentinel-1 images used here have medium spatial resolution. As seen at the figure 1, this image is formed by subswath IW1, IW2 and IW3 that Tehran is located on IW2.

Figure 1. left image is master and right image is slave Sentinel-1 image from Tehran

For assessment of the generated DEM from these stereo images, a reference DEM from Tehran with one-meter resolution has been used. These heights information are derived from terrestrial surveying and aerial photogrammetry methods. In this paper, SAR interferometry is used to generate DEM from Sentinel-1 stereo images.

3. SAR INTERFEROMETRY

SAR Interferometry is the method that determines phase differences between SAR images from one view. These images might have been taken from different positions or in different time. Phase difference obtained from SAR Interferometry contains several parameters. Some of these important parameters are orbital, topography, displacement, atmosphere and noise parameters. The effect of these parameter on phase difference is shown in equation 1.

$$\Delta\varphi_{int} = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} B^{\parallel} + \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \frac{B^{\perp}}{R_0 + \sin\theta} \varepsilon + \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} d_{los} + \Delta\varphi_{atmo} + \Delta\varphi_{noise} + 2\pi k \quad (1)$$

In this equation, $\Delta\varphi_{int}$ is SAR interferometry phase difference, λ is radar wavelength, R_0 is slant range from earth to sensor, θ is slant angle, B^{\parallel} and B^{\perp} are parallel and perpendicular of stereo images orbital differential, ε is topographic height of target pixel, d_{los} is terrain deformation, $\Delta\varphi_{atmo}$ is atmosphere effect phase difference and $\Delta\varphi_{noise}$ is noise phase difference. After removing the major trend of orbital phase difference (and considering other parameters negligible in comparison to phase difference), due to the fact that a radar sensor looks earth topography from two different sights, stereoscopy effect will be appeared. This topography parameter leads to topography fringes. Significant point is that deformation effect along the line sight of sensor can be achieved by removing orbital, topography and other effects. This process is not included in the topic of this paper. SAR interferometry process is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. SAR interferometry steps

4. DEM GENERATION USING SENTINEL-1 IMAGES

Generating DEM using sentinel-1 images and SAR interferometry is a multi-step process that is explained in the following. Due to the fact that sentinel-1 image cover large area of the earth, essential parts of the images can be to be split. Part of Tehran is located on IW1, so this part is separated from original images. The next important step is creating Interferogram. This step is done after co-registration between master and slave images. Interferogram is created by Complex multiplication. This multiplication is done pixel by pixel. The interferogram generated from sentinel-1 images is shown in figure 3. The Created interferogram also contains bursts. So debursting process is necessary. Due to various reasons such as natural condition, hard topography, error in co-registration processing and other reasons, interferogram image is noisy. So, goldstein filter is used for decreasing noise (Goldstein, 1998).

a) raw interferogram

b) interferogram image after debursting process

c) interferogram image after denoising by Goldstein filter

d) coherence image

Figure 3. Steps output of Implementation for Generate DEM using sentinel-1 image and SAR interferometry Process

The next step is unwrapping. SNAPHU is used for unwrapping (Chen, 2001). Slant range to ground range is done as the next step. Up to this step, generated DEM has not been reached to enough accuracy. GCPs must use for precise georeferencing of generated DEM. Alternative method is DEM Matching (Kim, 2011). generated DEM has a determined precision and this method (DEM matching) increase DEM accuracy using SRTM DEM (or other available DEMs). SRTM has an acceptable accuracy. This method does not require ground control points. In this paper to do the experiments, two part of Tehran are selected. One of these parts is mountain area and the other one is flat. The mountain area is located in north of Tehran and flat area is located in south of Tehran. Generated DEM in these two part are shown in figure 4

a) generated DEM from Southern part of Tehran

b) generated DEM from part of north Tehran

Figure 4. interferometric DEM generation using sentinel-1 images

5. RESULT

The precision of generated DEM was evaluated by comparing it to reference DEM. The results, as were expected, were more precise in flat areas. By generating a grid consist of 138761

points from flat area and another grid of 78196 points from mountain area in both DEMs, heights of these grid points are measured (figure 5) and the precision of generated DEM is evaluated.

a) flat area

b) mountain area

Figure 5. error occurred in generation of DEM

Digital numbers in Figure 5 images indicate the error occurred in generation of DEM. After applying 3σ test (blunder detection) and eliminating outliers, the standard deviation for generated DEM in flat area (south of Tehran) was 1.26 meters and in mountain area (north of Tehran) was 10.32 meters. Normalized histogram of occurred error on both DEMs are shown in figure 6. Horizontal direction is height error value and vertical units are percentage of occurred error.

Figure 6. Error occurred histogram in DEM generation

As shown in the figure, most occurred errors are less than about 10 meters; However, in some places occurred errors are more than 20 meters.

6. SUMMERY

Today with respect to technology improvement and new projects that are taken into account by new satellites, necessity of being able to process satellite images is more sensible. Generating DEM from these images is one of the topics that can be studied with these images. One of the last projects in satellite

remote sensing is Sentinel project that Sentinel-1 images are SAR images. This research is the study on generating DEM from Sentinel-1 images and SAR interferometry method. Images are taken from Tehran and the suburbs. For doing experiments, mountain and flat parts are used. The height precision calculated in mountain area was 10.32 meters and in flat area was 1.26 meters. The results show that Sentinel-1 images and SAR interferometry technique have the potential to generate DEM, especially in flat areas.

REFERENCES

Chen, C.W. and Zebker, H.A., 2001. Two-dimensional phase unwrapping with use of statistical models for cost functions in nonlinear optimization. *JOSA A*, 18(2), pp.338-351.

Eftekhari, A., Ghannadi, M.A., Motagh, M. and SaadatSeresht, M., 2013. D Object Coordinates Extraction by Radargrammetry and Multi Step Image Matching. *ISPRS-International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, (3), pp.147-151.

Ghannadi, M.A., Saadatseresht, M. and Motagh, M., 2015. Sentinel-1 Image Matching Using Strong Scatters. *The International Archives of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 40(1), p.233.

Goldstein, R.M. and Werner, C.L., 1998. Radar interferogram filtering for geophysical applications. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 25(21), pp.4035-4038.

Hu, J., Li, Z.W., Ding, X.L., Zhu, J.J., Zhang, L. and Sun, Q., 2014. Resolving three-dimensional surface displacements from InSAR measurements: A review. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 133, pp.1-17.

Kim, T. and Jeong, J., 2011. DEM matching for bias compensation of rigorous pushbroom sensor models. *ISPRS journal of photogrammetry and remote sensing*, 66(5), pp.692-699.

Lazecky, M., Comut, F.C., Qin, Y. and Perissin, D., 2017. Sentinel-1 Interferometry System in the High-Performance Computing Environment. In *The Rise of Big Spatial Data* (pp. 131-139). *Springer International Publishing*.

Makineci, H.B. and Karabörk, H., 2016. EVALUATION DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL GENERATED BY SYNTHETIC APERTURE RADAR DATA. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing & Spatial Information Sciences*, 41.

Yagüe-Martínez, N., Prats-Iraola, P., González, F.R., Brcic, R., Shau, R., Geudtner, D., Eineder, M. and Bamler, R., 2016. Interferometric processing of Sentinel-1 TOPS data. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 54(4), pp.2220-2234.